

ARCHITECTURAL AND CONSTRUCTION REQUIREMENTS IN THE DESIGN OF LOW-RISE RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS

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ABSTRACT

It is necessary to adopt architectural and engineering solutions, taking into account all the requirements for the object under construction. Architectural design affects the economic, technical, sanitary-hygienic, ecological, design and other aspects of residential buildings and structures, which are used as a basis for their further construction.

Keywords: *Low floor, residence, project, construction, design, architecture, premises, configuration.*

Architectural and construction projects are necessary for the construction of any residential and any real estate building, in which architectural and engineering solutions must be adopted taking into account all the requirements for the object under construction. Architectural design affects the economic, technical, sanitary-hygienic, ecological, design and other aspects of residential buildings and structures, which are used as a basis for their further construction. When choosing a construction site, in addition to its value, you should pay attention to the following conditions for the construction of a residential building: 1) easy access to traffic and the quality of access roads; 2) that the necessary engineering (heat, gas, water, electricity, sewage) and social (schools, hospitals, theaters, stadiums, etc.) infrastructures are provided; 3) environmental safety (closeness of industrial enterprises and agricultural production); 4) configuration, relief and orientation in relation to the sides of the horizon; 5) to construction in neighboring plots.

In fact, the most important thing when choosing a plot for construction is that the house you want to build on this plot does not belong to the category of "self-construction" and does not become an "outlaw" object, in order to solve problems that need to be solved in the future. If you have a skilled real estate agent, the deal can be done in a matter of months, or even faster. But you should use the services of a certified professional representative of a reliable and well-established real estate agency. When concluding a transaction, a real estate agency must reliably find and carefully check the following information: -Type of plot ownership (ownership/permanent use/inherited property/rental). - Check the authenticity and correctness of the registration of title documents with the seller and make sure that the seller has a certificate of title to the land, house or other structures (if any). Then you need to make sure that these documents are correctly drawn up and correctly registered. The list of documents may differ depending on the land category and ownership. -It is necessary to make sure that the owner of the property is the same person who has not changed his last name and is not registered anywhere. -It is necessary to know whether the plot has a legal dispute, is not mortgaged, the heirs of the original owner do not claim it. - Land plot cadastral plan. - Objects for sale can be only land plots registered in the state cadastre and assigned a state cadastral number. -The cadastral plan contains the following information: the location (address) of the land, its area, description of the boundaries, information about the category of land and the permitted use of the land, economic and quality characteristics, as well as information about the availability of real estate in the last 5 years. -Whether all necessary taxes and fees for the plot have been paid. If the owner of the property has arrears on payments, after the transaction is completed, all his debts will be transferred to the new owner along with the property. -Complete compliance of plot boundaries with all documents. In order to conclude a contract, the boundaries of the land plot must be clearly defined - its exact location on the ground, including the coordinates of the parties, length, area, land survey boundaries. The plot must be marked on the cadastral map, registered with the "State Committee for Land Resources, Geodesy, Cartography and State Cadastre of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and have a border status.

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